

VI International Forum on Teacher Education

Deviant Forms of Socialization of Personality in the Internet Space

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Abstract

The article discusses the problem of socialization of adolescents in online groups of deviant orientation. The study revealed significant differences in the needs of adolescents participating in online groups of deviant directions and normative adolescents. Teenagers with deviant behavior give more importance to their own status and membership in the Internet community, compared to normal teenagers. Our studies showed the presence among teenagers from deviant groups of the existing typologies that we studied and presented earlier: communicative deviants and adolescents with suicidal behavior of varying severity.

Keywords: teens, internet, deviant groups, socialization, needs.

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Published by Kazan federal university and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2020 (VI International Forum on Teacher Education)

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Introduction

Specific features of the Internet environment, such as efficiency, inclusion, lack of direct partner perception, anonymity, create favorable conditions for the socialization of the individual and can contribute to disruption of the socialization process and the occurrence of deviations in the development of the personality of Internet users. Unwillingness or inability to properly absorb the information culture of the Internet space, the presence of deviant motives for using the Internet and destructive ideas about it, can lead to a violation of the rules of interaction in the Internet environment and, as a result, to the formation of deviant forms of socialization of the person in the Internet space. To date, there is practically no empirical material that fully reveals and explains the problem of deviant personality behavior in virtual space. The study of the factors causing the manifestation of deviant forms of behavior in the Internet environment becomes significant.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is the analysis of deviant forms of personality socialization in the Internet space.

Literature review

The Internet is an ideal place to implement and "ripen" of deviant behavior. Teenagers are a group of Internet users most exposed to the mixed effects of a virtual environment. Various studies reveal that in the context of the age-specific nature of the moral, emotional sphere, they can provoke the commission of illegal actions in the Internet space.

In conditions of anonymity of the Internet space, communication with carriers of forms of deviant behavior is especially easily established. Variations of the negative impact can be establishing illegal contact with the teenager with the implementation of further criminal acts, cyber-harassment, cyberbullying, fraud and much more.

Bondarenko (2003; 2004) identifies the following factors contributing to the emergence of deviant forms of behavior in the Internet space:

- Lack of legal norms of behavior in the Internet environment;

- Lack of programs to control the behavior of minors in the network and qualified specialists who, at a professional level, carry out the prevention of deviant behavior in the virtual space;

- Attractiveness of “hackers” actions in the youth environment;
- Lack of demand for special knowledge of minors in the field of computer technology and, accordingly, the inability to self-actualize in any other way.

Mendelevich (2013) considers trolling, hacking, the activity of Internet scammers to deviant forms of behavior in the Internet space, etc. Virtual Internet communities of deviant behavior also include extremist religious sects, groups of economic terrorists, traditional and new organized criminal communities, some groups of young extremist orientations, etc.

Methodology

The study involved 143 respondents, including adolescents with normative online behavior (78 respondents) and adolescents with deviant behaviors (65 respondents) involved in the activities of deviant groups.

Research methods. The following methods were used in the study: expert assessments, questionnaires, content analysis in social networks, psychological tests. Psychodiagnostic techniques: a modified test of twenty statements by Kuhn (Rumyantseva, 2006); questionnaire "Who am I on the Internet" by McParland (Dahlberg, 2005; Toal, 2005); test "Personality in the virtual space" by Luchinkina (2012; 2013); test "Suicidal personality behavior in virtual space" by Luchinkina (2015); a modified test for diagnosing the degree of satisfaction of basic needs in the Internet space by Skvortsov (1986). CD-Quest was used to identify cognitive distortions.

Experiment description and procedure

At the first stage, according to the opinions of experts and the results of psychological diagnostics, user groups were identified with a normative and deviant direction of socialization in the Internet space. At the second stage, the psychological characteristics of users in these groups, their orientation, and accessible content were studied.

Results

According to experts (psychologists with at least 5 years of experience in this area) and based on the analysis of available content on the pages of users on the social network Vkontakte.ru, we distinguished groups of respondents with normative and deviant forms of behavior in the Internet space. To participate in the experiment, adolescents were invited, consisting of marginalized groups (teenage Internet subcultures) and Internet communities of an antisocial orientation: (shoplifters).

Self-image of adolescents of both selected groups. Results of a content analysis of the answers to the question “Who am I?” revealed significant differences in the responses of adolescents from the normative and deviant groups by the frequency of mentioning symbols of sexual preferences (macho, sexy frau, pretty girl, just sexy, heterosexual, sex machine): adolescents assigned to a group with a deviant form of socialization often resort to use such words in status, text than adolescents from the normative group. Comparison of percentages using the Fisher test showed that the differences are significant: 30% / 8%, φ critical = 2,9, $p \leq 0,01$.

The role position when teenagers describe their “I am on the Internet” is common. Teenagers in both samples turned to role positions such as user, gamer, troll, player, moderator, and others. Of course, adolescents' sexual preferences and assessments of leadership potential can be assigned without regard to the network, because of experience with peers. However, their presence once again shows that it is the Internet space that acts as a source of information about such an important area for teenagers as intimate.

The results of a study of the motivational and needful spheres of adolescents involved in groups with deviant forms of socialization showed that the basic needs include the need for external respect, security and the establishment of interpersonal relationships, $p \leq 0,01$. The least significant was the financial situation ($p \leq 0,05$).

The dominant needs of adolescents of the norm group in the Internet space are self-realization and financial situation, $p \leq 0,01$. The least expressed the need for security ($p \leq 0,05$).

Obviously, online teenagers with deviant behavior are trying to self-actualize and find ways of self-affirmation, acceptance. For them, contacts, communication implemented on the network, achievement of respect from the environment, and security are also significant. The degree of satisfaction of the Internet needs among adolescents in the samples is different: for deviant adolescents, the need for respect from users (the difference between the indicators is 4 points), security (5 points difference) and interpersonal relationships (3 points difference) were more significant, compared to normative teens.

Validation of differences in indicators on the scales of the methodology of Skvortsov (1986) using the Mann-Whitney criterion allowed us to draw the following conclusions: deviant adolescents are more focused on receiving confirmation of their own significance in the Internet space, respect ($U = 531,50$, $p = 0,053$), gaining security ($U=1594$, $p = 0,050$) in contrast with teens in the normative group. Material values were less significant for deviant adolescents compared to normative adolescents ($U = 549,00$, $p = 0,05$).

An analysis of the pages on the social networks of adolescents of both groups showed that adolescent deviant groups used their own names (18%), the names of the heroes of computer games, films (40%), neutral nicknames (angel, displeased, bored, Alina - love and others (42%). At the same time, adolescents from the normative group gravitated to the names of animals, birds and other representatives of flora and fauna (19%), but also used the names of the heroes of computer games, films (38%), proper names (43%).

The specifics of choosing photos for avatars in both groups of teenagers is interesting. In deviant groups, self-photos are more often chosen, where there are glasses on the face, bangs on the face, a hat or cap on the head (25%); personal photos, but from the back or in profile (20%); anime (20%); heroes of computer games, comics (25%); animals (10%).

Avatars of teenagers with normative behavior are as follows: own photo in a favorable perspective, selfie (45%). A photo where there are glasses, a bang, a hat or a cap is revealed in 10%; someone else's photo (10%); anime (20%); heroes of computer games, comics (20%); animals (5%).

Thus, the differences lie in the angle and quality of the submitted photos. Differences were found in relation to selfies, where there are glasses on the face, the face is covered with bangs. The share of such photos on the pages of adolescents from deviant groups is significantly different from the share of photos of adolescents from the normative group (25%/10%, φ critical = 2,45, $p \leq 0,05$).

Analysis of posts on social networks of adolescents from both samples showed that their nature is different. Next, we describe them in accordance with the frequency of placement: the most placed are entertainment posts, the less represented are the sale and purchase posts. The intensity of the placement is as follows: entertainment posts (humor, joke) amounted to 50%; quotes from great philosophers, famous people and the like made up 45%. Note that the use of quotes, statements can indicate both in favor of creativity, and at a young age.

News posts accounted for about 38%; emotional posts reflecting feelings, mood, filled with pictures and statements about good / evil, joy, hate / love, etc. made up 100% of adolescents. Reasoning, where adolescents share their own point of view with others about different events, things and people, was 40% of adolescents from deviant groups and 25% of adolescents from the normative group. Educational posts occupied only 10% of the total.

Advertising posts are typical for 20% of adolescents. Motivational posts containing calls for action (gathering a volunteer movement, helping someone, making money on the Internet, becoming famous and

others) are more often found among normative adolescents (40%) than among adolescents from deviant groups (18%).

There were also aggressive posts (attacks on other users, cyberbullying, etc.) in 32% of deviant adolescents and 5% of normative adolescents. The presence of aggression in the network manifests itself in a sufficiently large number of adolescents of both sexes, reflecting their negativity and aggressiveness (32%).

According to the results of the analysis of activity in social networks, by comparing the percentages in the samples of adolescents from deviant groups and adolescents from the normative group, significant differences were revealed. Normative adolescents more often place reasoning and motivational posts than adolescents from deviant groups: 40%/18%, 40%/25%, φ critical = 2,65, $p < 0,05$. Aggressive posts were more often recorded in adolescents from deviant groups (32%/5%, φ critical = 2,95, $p < 0,001$). Identified gender features: emotional posts and posts-quotes more often placed girls more often than boys ($p = 0,01$).

To assess the orientation of the person in Internet communication, the method of Luchinkina "Personality in the virtual space" was used (Luchinkina; 2013). Studies of personality orientation in virtual communication showed that prosociality is expressed in 21 people (43%) (of which 2 adolescents from deviant groups (10%), and in adolescents with normal behavior 19 (90%)), a tendency to asocial behavior in 22 people have a social network (45%) (of which 19 are teenagers from deviant groups (86%) and 3 are teenagers (14%) from the normative), 6 people have an antisocial network (12%) (4 of them (67%) adolescent from deviant groups and 2 (33%) from normative groups).

Discussions

1. The importance of belonging to a group in social networks for adolescents.

The results of the study indicate that deviant adolescents are more involved in the Internet space than adolescents with normative behavior. In particular, they are interested in various Internet subcultures and in which of them they will be composed, and in general their role in certain Internet communities. For deviant adolescents, the need for self-realization, respect and safety, in contrast to adolescents with normative behavior, turned out to be more significant. The significance of status and belonging to a certain group in the network distinguishes deviant adolescents from their peers with normative behavior. This indicates a lack of a sense of significance among peers or close circle in the real world, which is offset by the desire to establish contacts and set likes. While belonging to a certain group in the network compensates for the lack of friends in reality.

2. Is it possible to distinguish the typology of adolescents involved in the activities of deviant groups?

The study identified several groups of adolescents with deviant behavior, depending on the severity of their virtuality, level of orientation, type of unmet need, personal mythology, and type of cognitive distortion. Our studies have shown the presence of existing typologies among adolescents from deviant groups that we studied and presented earlier: communicative deviants. In this group, several subgroups can be distinguished such as trolls, spammers, flooders, cyberbullers and victims, adolescents with imitative behavior. There are also teenagers with suicidal behavior of varying severity: imitators, artists, suicides, spectators. Moreover, the results described above were common for the entire specified group.

Conclusion

Teenagers with deviant behavior place more emphasis on their own status and membership in the Internet community, compared to normal teenagers ($p \leq 0,05$). The leading needs realized on the Internet for deviant adolescents turned out to be self-realization, gaining respect from the environment, and ensuring safety. They are less focused on material values in the Internet space, more often seek to fulfill the needs for security and confirm their own significance ($p \leq 0,05$).

Thus, the deviant forms of socialization of a person in the Internet space are caused by the conscious or unconscious use of information technology to perform various destructive influences in order to cause economic, moral or physical harm (and self-harm).

Recommendations

An update and high-quality development of new effective means of prevention and correction of deviant forms of behavior in the Internet space is necessary.

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